

TREEHOUSE ARCHITECTURE AS
DISASTER-RESILIENT SHELTER:
Ecological and Structural
strategies.

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TREEHOUSES ARCHITECTURE AS DISASTER-RESILIENT SHELTER: ECOLOGICAL AND STRUCTURAL STRATEGIES FOR VULNERABLE REGIONS.

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ABSTRACT

This paper suggests treehouses as a disaster-prone shelter prototype for regions under a high impact damage risk. Based on precedent literature, ecological data and structural design principles, it examines how tree-integrated shelters can mitigate floods, tsunamis, hurricanes and other natural hazards, while promoting local forest restoration and particular care to trees at arboricultural level. The research highlights key tree species with structural and regenerative traits suitable for long-term resilience and treehouse samples around the world that could be used as a design template for temporary or long-term shelter modules. Findings suggest that treehouse shelters offer a sustainable, low-impact and low cost and modular emergency construction alternatives for displaced communities.

KEYWORDS:

Treehouse architecture; Disaster-resilient shelter; Sustainable design; Ecological adaptation; Modular emergency shelter;

1. INTRODUCTION

Did you also dream about a treehouse as a kid? For many, the idea of a treehouse evokes childhood dreams of escape and adventure. Yet beyond nostalgia lies a powerful architectural opportunity: elevated shelters that could withstand floods, storms, and seismic events. For many years, communities living in disastrous areas suffered from constant housing renovation caused by natural factors like storms, strong winds, floods etc. These people were finding solution in rebuilding and recovering their homes, but what if the answer is in looking upward, towards trees?

Treehouses were mostly an object of entertainment, serving children. But if we look beyond, they are more than just a playhouse. It is a type of elevated structure which is commonly used by other creatures as a nook, a nest, and of course as a shelter. Animals weren't the only ones to seek shelter from trees, from history people have settled in trees to hide from predators, to survive in floods and to cover from rainfalls (Babris and Bratuškis, 2019). Today treehouses are also an artistic and unique approach to tourism industry as such hotels provide direct connection with nature and a deep insight into forests or protected landscapes. From an architectural perspective it is an easy and quick assembly structure that can both be seasonal or yearlong dwelling (Babris and Bratuškis, 2019). While serving as a tourist attraction, on the

other side of the world it might help people whose houses are left with permanent damage due to frequent natural disasters. According to a research, top 30 countries which suffered severe damage from natural hazards are listed starting from United States. Followed by Mexico, Chile, Brazil, Canada, Cuba and Argentina. There are also new faces, like Italy, Germany, France and United Kingdom from Europe. The list contains many Asian countries, such as China Japan, Thailand, India, and Koreas.(Shen *et al.*, 2018). As seen from the results, we can observe risks of fatality, injury, property loss in almost all corners of the world.

fig.1 Disaster impact risks

Here you can see the map with shown risks of expected disaster impacts by country. Fatality risk of expected disaster (a); injury risk of expected disaster (b); affected people risk from expected disaster (c); damage risk of expected disaster (d); (Shen *et al.*, 2018).

Traditional solutions to these problems, most common of which is floods, are mostly drainage systems or levees. Many years ago, New Orleans engineer

Lewis De Russey suggested an idea—building above the flood risk. His idea was to deploy the flood in controlled manner and adjust the infrastructure around it (Day and Erdman, 2018). While this solution was suggested in mid-19th century, Native Americans coped with floodplain in similar ways before the land was occupied by Europeans. They settled atop terraces near the river upstream. According to Archeologists, the foundation of these settlements was excessive amount of clam shells extracted by natives. Additionally, Europeans encountered building practices imported from the Caribbean called *poteaux-en-terre*, which was used in French colonial settlements.

fig. 2 Poteaux-en-terre

The strategy was to insert large vertical posts into the ground and fill the spaces with mud and moss mixture known as *bousillage*. These constructions could withstand nearly annual floods (Colten, 2001). Looking at the image, one can observe tree trunks used as columns and beams for elevating the structure. However, this could be done without harming the tree and using the trunk and

canopy as a loadbearing system. As observed from history, people of past coped with floods by elevating their homes and pinning them deep down to the ground. But there is a ready structure that is both elevated and rooted deeply into the earth: Trees.

fig.3 Post disaster property damage

This image demonstrates how severely properties of habitats are damaged, while the trees local to the area are intact with all the leaves.

fig.4 Post disaster property damage

This paper suggests that Treehouses, when built on disaster prone regions, could be a potential, sustainable shelter solution protecting from multiple natural hazards, by leveraging the structural resilience of certain tree species.

2. CONCEPTUAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Housing vulnerability in disastrous regions.

Natural disasters cause tremendous damage to communities living in risk zones for decades. Millions of people suffer from floods, extreme winds, typhoons, tsunamis, and such, annually. Unfortunately, these cases are under-investigated, as people have no choice rather than returning to the same spot after losing their belongings, properties, and maybe even close ones. After the danger is gone, they start their lives over again, and as the next step start looking for shelter. Some try to rebuild their damaged properties; some try to relocate and find a place somewhere else. According to a study investigating safety perceptions of communities that rebuilt their houses which were damaged after a natural hazard, people that did not get any assistance from the recovery organization, tend to mimic the structure of the damaged house, in order to gain their house back (“extending-impact-2015,” no date). Households that did receive assistance, on the other hand, were investigated by local engineers to identify vulnerabilities of the structure and design advanced alternatives. Even in cases when organizations can directly provide a new house, it is important to be trained to build against hazards, (Venable *et al.*, 2021), as well as building safe shelters in times of danger.

2.2 Treehouses as a transitional shelter option.

After a demolishing disaster, people struggle with finding a cover over their heads, since rebuilding requires time, effort, and resources. While trying to return to their normal lives, victims of mass damage face a gap between disaster and final resettlement, which could be filled with temporary housing (Johnson, Lizarralde and Davidson, 2006), (Johnson, 2007; Arslan and Cosgun, 2008). Such housing is provided for enough time for reconstruction and designing alternative options to build more resistant properties. These units could be used on two occasions: As a post disaster temporary housing, relying on trees that are guaranteed to survive extreme weather damage, and before emergency, to protect from potential injuries during upcoming demolishing hazards.

The key factors of successful shelter are:

- Security
- Interior climate comfort
- Basic action space requirement
- Visual comfort
- Air quality
- Flexibility in space and form
- Aesthetics
- Avoiding environmental pollution of any kind
- No harmful emissions
- Using recyclable sustainable materials
- Easy production and construction

- Assembly in several steps
- Acoustic and visual privacy

(Şener and Altun, no date). If we compare common properties of treehouses, we will observe a very similar pattern, suggesting that treehouses are a suitable option to be considered a shelter. According to the “Design of a post disaster shelter unit” paper that examined shelter units across the world to find the best one for Istanbul earthquake victims, ideal material for building a high-quality shelter, is wood. Some of the criteria for perfect shelter are:

- Avoiding environmental pollution of any kind
- No harmful emission related to materials
- Using recyclable materials
- Sustainability
- Easy construction and assembly

Wood as a material fulfills the design criteria of “avoiding environmental pollution of any kind”, and “no harmful emission related to materials”, “using recyclable materials”, and “sustainability”. Unit shall be constructed from prefabricated wood panels to fill the criteria of “ease of construction”. The unit should be made of wooden sandwich panels to fit the criteria or “interior comfort”. Unit shall have a prefabricated foundation to fit into “temporary interaction with the ground” criteria.

Namely, treehouse construction fits most of the listed criteria including the prefabricated foundation, as treehouses don’t need any foundation installed as the trunk and the roots already act as a durable sustainable and environmental foundation which eliminates time consumed on building a new foundation, making treehouse shelter a faster construction in comparison with other shelter prototypes.

2.3 Disaster durable tree species suitable for treehouses.

Building a treehouse process starts with finding the right tree. In this section we will discuss trees species that are both durable to hold a house and withstand natural hazards.

2.3.1 Oak trees.

First on the list is certainly Oak trees:

fig. 5 Live Oak tree

To be specific, Oak species are in descending order, first being the most durable:

- Sand live Oak
- Live Oak
- Laurel Oak

University of Florida IFAS researched 6 hurricanes, 4 of which were in panhandle Florida (Erin, Dennis, Opal, Ivan) and 2 in south Florida (Jeanne, Charley), found that in comparison with other trees, these three species had minimal impact overall, which makes them highest in survival rate.

fig 6. (Duryea and Kampf, 2007)

As seen from the graph, Sand Oak and Live Oak performed between 95-100% survival, while Laurel Oak also showed high result between 75-95%. Although it is not ideal, researchers believe it is related to soil type, as south Florida's sandy soil isn't the natural habitat of this tree (Duryea and Kampf, 2007). Still many authors mention Live Oaks as trees with little failure in hurricanes (Gresham, Williams and Lipscomb, 1991a). An interesting fact is that these Oaks, along with other durable tree species that will be mentioned later, grow usually at lower coastal plains, and face hurricanes more than inland species (Barry, 1998). Commonly, lifespan of these trees is at least a century, living

from 400 to 600 years. Looking at the average 5.8 recurrence intervals of hurricanes in this area, these trees would be exposed to 17 hurricanes in 100 years lifetime. Therefore, it is possible that over time these trees have naturally grow to guard against intense winds, making them naturally durable to such disasters (Gresham, Williams and Lipscomb, 1991b).

2.3.2 Pine trees.

Another tree worth to mention is a Pine tree:

fig. 7 Longleaf Pine tree

A few of Pines were researched and concluded with most resistant being:

- Longleaf Pine
- Loblolly Pine

The uniqueness of these trees is that they grow very tall and despite the height, during ravaging hurricanes, minimal damage is observed only to the crown part. According to (Garms and Dean, 2019), the longer the tree, the more it is sturdy and breakage proof. A 300-year-old Longleaf Pine will endure nearly 50 tropical storms, throughout its

lifetime, even in inland portions. To maximize their resistance to hurricanes, some actions should be taken. Starting from avoiding roads and edges and any new structures integrated into the soil. To restore the Longleaf Pine forest, new stands should be planted next to the existing ones, to increase their survival rate (Whelan *et al.*, 2024). Generally, for such trees to perform their best, they should receive care from professionals in arboriculture.

2.3.3 Tupelo trees.

Next is a tree highly resistant to both floods and hurricanes, Swamp Tupelo:

fig. 8 Swamp Tupelo

This tree is able to withstand multiple natural hazards, making it suitable for shelter consideration. While hurricanes raze entire villages, Tupelos are affected lightly in terms of few upper branches (Gresham, Williams and Lipscomb, 1991b). Swamp Tupelos have high flood tolerance as experiments show that they grow in both flooded and well-drained moist soils, meaning they don't necessarily grow in water reservoirs. It was also observed that they not only tolerate floods but continue growing and

releasing new seedlings. These trees' roots are also observed to tolerate high concentrations of Carbon Dioxide emissions, (Hook, Brown and Kormanik, 1971), making them ecologically advantageous as they can survive in polluted waters and risks of future climate changes.

2.3.4 Cypress trees.

Tree very similar to Swamp Tupelo is next in the list, Bald Cypress:

fig. 9 Bald Cypress

Cypresses and Tupelos, along with looking very similar, have almost same properties. Besides being flood resistant, Bald Cypresses have shown high tolerance to salinity as well. While ideal condition for a Cypress is neither extremely wet nor extremely dry, (Mitsch and Ewel, 1979), a hurricane can cause a sudden increase in salt levels in water habitats of these trees (Day *et al.*, 2024). Studies have repeatedly concluded that Bald Cypresses are salinity tolerant. Even though after shallow flooding, seedlings exhibited lower stomatal conductance, they eventually recovered within three

weeks(Pezeshki, Delaune and Patrick, 1987). Another short-term experiment watered one set of trees daily with salt water and another set with adding fresh water once a week, have concluded with similar results, showing reduced diameter in growth but increased density in wood and greater resistance to embolism and xylem cavitation, in another words survival to drought (Petek-Petrik *et al.*, 2023). Comparing Cypress seedlings from parents grown in fresh waters and seedlings from parents grown in saline solutions, salty seedlings were more tolerant indicating genetic mutation to adapt into the environment (Allen, Chambers and McKinney, 1994).

2.3.5 Mangrove trees.

One of the unique species among trees is certainly a Mangrove tree:

fig.10 Mangrove tree

Mangrove trees are known for their extraordinary root system. They grow by crossing each other and swooped into

the soil, which makes them durable to face seawater waves. Besides being tangled, roots also have a chewy nature, which is not easily broken or cut. In a distant village of Indonesia called Tongke-Tongke, these trees are used commonly for their properties. The elasticity helps to hold water waves constantly, facing strong waves with ease. They are used as a natural barrier to protect land borders from washing away, by keeping the rising water stable, minimizing risks of flooding. One of the natural hazards that threaten coastal communities is whirlwinds. Before spreading the Mangrove ecosystem, these winds were scattering house parts like roofs or walls. After ecosystem spread over 2.5 km coastline, number of the damaged houses significantly decreased, which makes it safe to say that Mangrove trees withstand hurricanes and protect the village behind, from mass distractions. Another important fact about these species is that the roots have a unique water filtration system, allowing villagers to save on water sources as the groundwater becomes drinkable after salty seawater passes through root biofilter. This provides them both with drinkable and usable water sources for the households (Sambu and Amruddin, 2018).

There's certainly more to this list, but there's no research-based proof to indicate them. Despite not being mentioned particularly, there are some

ways to predict a tree's resistance performance in an upcoming natural disaster. Trees with some properties have shown better results in durability, first and the most obvious being trunk density, combined with greater modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity. Observations also show that conifers tend to be less wind resistant in comparison with angiosperms (flowering trees). Comparing deciduous trees to evergreens, we can similarly observe that deciduous trees have more wind tolerance (Salisbury *et al.*, 2025). Investigating last hurricanes in Florida, researches have concluded that native trees are more hurricane resistant than exotic species,(Duryea and Kampf, 2007), recommending to search for natives of the area and plant them in hopes of restoring hurricane resistant forests. It is also very important to work with arborists and regulate post hurricane conditions of trees and keep the health of trees in control together with occasional pruning. They also should be planted in groups of at least five, with enough distance to avoid root collapse for trees to develop strong supporting root system, to achieve minimum tree mortality. Other trees that have been mentioned in durable tree records are, American Elm, Palm species, Douglas Fir, Alpine Larch, Western Larch, Whitebark Pine, Jack Pine, Ponderosa Pine, Black Cottonwood etc. ("tree_species_resistance_and_risk," no date). Looking at these trees, it is easy to

notice that they are mostly broadleaf species, which is related to absorbing the shock from winds, and thus being less affected by them, due to complex branching and architecture (Jackson *et al.*, 2021). This proves that treehouses built on trees resistant to certain extreme weather types like storms, floods, hurricanes, or else, should be a safe shelter prototype for communities suffering from such natural hazards.

3. ARCHITECTURAL IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Construction materials and techniques.

Treehouses typically play the role of a playhouse for children, but in this case scenario they need to function as a safe haven for communities who are at risk of facing a disaster in no time. With tree canopy absorbing the shock from winds, and roots providing structural integrity of the trunk, ideal place for the house would be few meters above the ground, anchored to the trunk without causing any damage.

A paper published by Riga Technical University discusses their experience of building public treehouses in Latvia and how it works as a tool to bring communities closer. According to the paper, it is allowed to build on Oak trees in Latvia, which is a top candidate in our compatible trees list, and Pines which is also a good choice for a house amongst a set of trees. Nowadays it is easier to obtain structural properties of trees using modern 3D scanning methods,

which is a big asset in correctly positioning the treehouse. As mentioned, it is easier to work with Pines since they grow in close groups, allowing them to be connected via short beams. They also provide great load-bearing wood capacity by pierced bolts up to 23kN.

There are three main groups of load transfer types: tree canopy-based structures, structures with separate foundation for load transfer distribution, and frames with intermediate load transfer solutions. Since the trees suggested for the shelter are mainly hard wood options with dense trunks and complex root system, the category most used would be canopy-based solutions. Speaking about structure types, it is also important to choose the right fastener types to attach and secure the house. Here are five main types:

- Bolt fasteners-metal joints like pins, anchors, nails and bolts drilled or nailed into the wood.
- Hanging treehouses.
- Structures with partial load transfer to artificial support.
- Organically, tree-supported treehouses.

- Ring constrictors-using pieces as permanent metal hoops or elastic knot system. (Babris and Bratuškins, 2019)

fig.11 Wooden ring constrictor

The safest way to assemble the house without any harm to the tree would most certainly be ring constrictors.

Not many architectural companies specialize in treehouse construction, thus not much educational literature is available. Most of the existing treehouses are built by enthusiast or adventure park construction companies. Such structures are common in different corners of the world; almost all communities are acquainted with them at some point in history. Treehouses are witnessed the most in Central Europe, United States, Equatorial climate zones close to South, East of China sea and Sea of Japan. They are often used as hotels, houses, sightseeing platforms, attractions, treetop tents, restaurants and cafes, office spaces, outdoor cinemas, camping areas etc. which gives a clue that there are treehouses that already fully function and their prototype could be used as a shelter module.

Lightweight fastener can be very useful if the shelter must be assembled on site, fast and with ease. There's also a knotting system adopted from Netherlands, and was tested on practical models, and the outcome was that it has almost unnoticeable effect on the tree trunk (Babris and Bratuškis, 2019). mention that they built public treehouse during a workshop that lasted two weeks, and they managed to build seven platforms which contained a pop-up café, game room, watch tower, hammock lounge, concert platforms and installed a climbing net. They used nature friendly knot system which is the best fit for short term activities and pop-up events. Even though this workshop was for team building and a fun activity to bring people together, it is important to mention that all the functions above are fully suitable to include in shelter prototype. As they mentioned, knot system is the easiest, fastest, and most affordable way to secure a structure to the tree, which is the main criteria of immediate shelter unit. Their multistorey treehouse stayed in the park for almost two years and gained popularity by visitors.

According to multiple sources available online, the best sustainable and affordable materials for treehouses are:

- Engineered Timber
- Reclaimed Wood
- Bamboo
- Weatherproof Plywood and Composite Panels

(www.e-a-a.com/sustainable-materials-for-building-and-decorating-treehouses, treeabouts.com/treehouse-building-materials-what-works-best).

3.2 Safety standards and structural integrity.

To create a safe shelter, all safety precautions should be fulfilled, starting with railing around the house to prevent falling especially for children. The deck surface should be finished with slip-proof materials. To access the house conveniently, fixed stairs or a ramp, considering disabled people, are the best options. In case of falling, below the treehouse should be a falling zone covered with materials like shredded bark, wood chips or rubber mulch, to act as a cushion for accidental falls (engineerfix.com/how-to-make-a-treehouse-from-planning-to-building).

3.3 Community integration in shelter building.

Building shelters should be community practice, to bring people together and build a closer circle to single handedly survive and recover from upcoming disasters. It is true that working as a team brings both moral and physical security. Action research on community engagement in forest restoration in rural areas of Zimbabwe, shows impacts of collaborating with locals including youngsters and children. They noticed positive outcomes on people's wellbeing and livelihood. This project encouraged other organizations, schools and

universities to take part in such activities (Bayley *et al.*, 2025). This research supports the idea of teaching building safe shelters as a standard practice in risk zones and provide people with simple kits to help assemble treehouses autonomously.

3.4 Reference projects for elevated shelter design.

Even though shelters in treehouses haven't been realized yet, there are some useful treehouse designs, that can serve as inspiration for future prototypes.

3.4.1 Magnolia and Fir.

"Magnolia and Fir" is a treehouse by a German firm specializing in arboreal architecture, called Baumraum:

fig. 12 Magnolia and Fir treehouse

It was built in 2007, as a private property in Westphalia, Germany. As mentioned in the name, the house is built between magnolia and several fir trees. It consists of one enclosed cube and one open terrace. Tatajuba, which is weather-proof wood, was used on the exterior and terrace. Interior, on the other hand, is made of reddish oak. It is mainly used as a guest room or an office

space by the owners. This design is significant in means of prototype value, exemplifying how elevated can combine structural integrity, multiuse functionality and aesthetical sophistication. It is a sustainable solution with durable woods and minimal ground impact aligning with design principles. In terms of safety and engineering, company's precise steel framework and material choices show that this house will stand for many years, serving as a family heirloom (www.baumraum.de).

3.4.2 Les Nids.

Next treehouse is in UNESCO-listed watchmaking town in Jura Mountains in Switzerland. It functions as an alternative to traditional hotels offering immersion into nature:

fig. 13 Les Nids treehouses

"Les Nids" (French for "The Nest") is a set of 4 treehouses built in 2002–2005 in Le Locle. They are timber-framed cabins typically 5–8 meters above the ground, designed to last at least twenty years. It is almost fully functioning house with a kitchenette, bathroom with shower and WC, wood-burning stove and sleeping

space for 2-5 guests depending on the unit. This example is a valuable prototype which could be mimicked in shelter design, fitting almost all shelter criteria. It is a semi-permanent structure with minimal environmental impact, implying forest preservation and sustainable eco-architecture goals (www.lesnids.ch).

3.4.3 Temple of the blue moon.

Treehouse “Temple of the blue moon” is designed by Pete Nelson, founder of Treehouse Point:

fig. 14 Temple of blue moon treehouse

This treehouse is located in Issaquah, Washington, USA—nestled in an old forest along with a spring-fed river. Built in early 2000s, “Temple of the blue moon” was the first treehouse on the property. It is built on 300-year-old 160-foot Stika spruce tree and could be accessed by a bridge across a slope leading to the entrance. Inside one can find a sleeping zone, handcrafted kitchenette, study area, small living area, combined with a balcony overlooking to the river. It is part of the larger treehouse village, offering guided tours, workshops and glamping experience. This serves as an example

for designing and building treehouse communities, as a shelter zone (www.treehousepoint.com).

3.4.4 Tree Tents.

Next is a Tree Tent example, founded by UK-based studio with global reach:

fig. 15 Tree Tent

Mission was to create a low impact architecturally refined wilderness structure for eco-tourism, conservation and off-grid living, emergency or seasonal shelter. It is a suspended structure hanging between trees using tension cables and lightweight framing. CNC-cut marine plywood, recycled aluminum airframe, technical waterproof fabric and natural wood insulation was used to create this spherical pod. It is 3 meters in diameter and fully customizable, including interior layout, insulation type, canvas color, furnishings. It can be assembled in remote or difficult terrains, designed for forests, hillsides, and remote natural settings, installed with minimal ground impact and no permanent foundation. This pod is a great shelter prototype for flooding regions, serving as a easily

attachable structure to hold on during floodplain (treetents.co.uk).

fig. 16 Layout and Section

4. CONCLUSION

This study has explored treehouse architecture as a disaster-resilient shelter typology, emphasizing ecological adaptation and structural efficiency. Treehouses can offer a solution to challenges faced by disaster-prone regions, whether it is temporary or long-term situation, by elevating habitats from vulnerable ground conditions or extreme weather dangers, integrating resilient tree species and using modular construction techniques. This solution will not only serve as a safer environment for communities suffering from hazards but also encourage care for the local forests and surrounding vegetation.

Further research should expand on refine materials, construction logistics and community acceptance. Designing a descent prototype using sustainable solutions to create self-sufficient and quick assembly unit, that could be customized for needs of users, including hazard type, local materials availability

and amount of people it will accommodate.

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